

The Varieties of Universal Expansion: Eddington and the Complexities of Early Cosmology

Matthew Stanley

*New York University, Gallatin School of Individualized Study, New York, NY,
10003, USA*

Abstract. A.S. Eddington was one of the handful of astronomers conversant with the many observational and theoretical factors at play in early 20th-century cosmology. Early relativistic cosmology touched on deep issues in several fields, and these diverse disciplinary requirements gave rise to a great deal of confusion about precisely what “expansion” meant and what implications that had for the construction of cosmological models. Eddington’s efforts to resolve these difficulties help show the profound technical, conceptual, and philosophical difficulties that attended early ideas regarding an expanding universe.

1. Introduction

A hundred years ago, there were no cosmologists. There were people who studied the cosmos, but they called themselves astronomers, physicists, or mathematicians. There was no standard training, no shared expectations, no methods agreed upon for investigating the universe as a whole. These disciplinary splits were serious obstacles for the development of early expanding universe cosmologies. A particularly important difficulty was the relationship between theory and observation in talking about the entire universe. There was significant disagreement about what theory could - and should - explain, particularly with respect to the question of beginnings. There was even uncertainty about what counted as an observation, and what role observations should play in the new cosmologies. The example of A.S. Eddington (1882-1944), a central participant in these early debates, helps show the details of these struggles and how he helped resolve them. Eddington was the Plumian Professor of astronomy at Cambridge, where he arrived with an unusual background. He had studied physics in Manchester, mathematics at Cambridge, and was then chief assistant at the Royal Observatory Greenwich. This gave him a diverse set of skills, all of which turned out to be essential for grappling with the challenges of early relativistic cosmologies.

2. De Sitter’s Theory

A good place to begin studying the disciplinary difficulties of early relativistic cosmologies is with the general confusion about the meaning of Willem de Sitter’s solutions to Einstein’s field equations. De Sitter’s theory became known to the astronomy community through Eddington. The Great War was raging, and Eddington was one of the very few scientists willing to disseminate ideas across national boundaries (Stanley 2003).

He became a nexus for relativity: making papers available, interpreting them for those unfamiliar with the difficult mathematics, and popularizing the essential ideas and implications. De Sitter's theory had a peculiar feature that has made it a popular candidate for the first suggestion of an expanding universe. He proposed that in certain circumstances, distant bodies would have their spectra shifted into the red. The significance of this "de Sitter effect" seems obvious in retrospect, but at the time its meaning was extremely ambiguous. There were actually two separate phenomena called by this name: first, that test particles will tend to move apart in a de Sitter universe, and second, that objects at the edge of the universe would appear to be redshifted due to time dilation. It is important to emphasize that originally it was not at all clear that these effects had any relation to each other. In terms of the contemporary understandings of general relativity there was no real reason to expect a connection between these two effects. A redshift did not imply an expanding universe.

Eddington was unusual among scientists of the time in that he was deeply conversant with both general relativity and cutting-edge astronomical observations. In particular, he knew about Vesto Slipher's amazingly precise work on redshifts of spiral nebulae. The spirals, as apparently vastly distant objects, were good candidates for observing the de Sitter effect (whatever it might be). In Eddington's first publication on relativity, his 1918 Report, he was uncertain how best to connect Slipher's observations with theory. First he commented that they indicated "very large observed velocities," which suggests that he was thinking in terms of physical movement. But then he noted that redshifts were interpreted as movement only "in practice" and could well be "spurious" (Eddington 1918, p. 89). The redshifts might be purely relativistic and not Doppler shifts at all. He continued struggling with how to interpret the redshifts for years to come:

This may be a genuine phenomenon in the evolution of the material universe; but it is also possible that the interpretation of spectral displacement as a receding velocity is erroneous; and the effect is really the slowing of atomic vibrations predicted by de Sitter's theory. (Eddington 1920, p. 161)

He seemed to be pulled toward a Doppler interpretation by Slipher's observations, but the alternative time dilation interpretations continued to nag at him. He noted certain paradoxes that arose with the pure time dilation interpretation, but continued to warn that the redshift could be "erroneously interpreted as a motion of recession" (Eddington 1923, p. 161). His attempt to split the difference between these effects with his "anticipation" idea - that the apparent velocity of an observed spiral only became genuine after the transit time of the light - did not help resolve anything (Eddington 1923). It is important to be clear that by the mid-1920s Eddington was certainly not persuaded that the universe was expanding. He repeatedly used Slipher's measurements but was not at all sure about their relationship to the relativistic models available (at this point, really only the Einstein and de Sitter worlds). The measurements certainly did not cleanly decide between them. The redshifts had no strong meaning to him on their own - they were only observations. In terms of comparing the available models, he thought the Einstein universe had more interesting physics, and that the de Sitter universe had more appeal for astronomers by perhaps explaining the apparent recession of the spirals. Eddington also considered that de Sitter's proposal would not be welcome to the followers of Mach due to its lack of matter. This was a serious issue because most of those deeply conversant with the physics and mathematics of general relativity

(Einstein chief amongst them) continued to think of the theory in Machian terms (Eddington 1918, p. 90). Eddington hoped for a middle ground between the Einstein and de Sitter universes that could be palatable to both astronomers and physicists.

3. Conversion to an expanding universe

The typical benchmark for a shift toward an expanding universe is Hubble's 1929 paper (Hubble 1929), but that definitely was not the case for Eddington. He was not particularly excited by Hubble's work, and he continued relying mostly on Slipher's results well into the 1930s. He was only willing to accept an expanding universe as a result of theoretical developments, not observational ones. When Lemaître's 1927 paper¹ resurfaced in 1930, Eddington worked hard to make sure it was widely known. It was exactly the intermediate solution between the Einstein and de Sitter universes for which he had been looking. He credited Lemaître with having shown that the universe was expanding (Eddington 1931b). De Sitter's theory, he said, only gave an "an imitation recession" (Eddington 1933, p. 2).

So why was Eddington in 1933 persuaded that there was a genuine recession? Again, it was not the Hubble observations. Those were only useful, he said, once they had been made sense of by Lemaître's theory. He argued over and over that theory was the key to making the expanding universe real. He said it would be a mistake to "regard the 'expansion of the universe' as an observational phenomenon independent of the theories of curved space" (Eddington 1931a, p. 412). The recession of the spirals could not be considered in isolation from the theories that explained the redshifts. He described observations as falling into line with theory, and indeed having been foretold by theory (Eddington 1933, pp. 14-5 and Eddington 1930, p. 677) He pushed even further in claiming the expanding universe for the theorists. He admonished observers for not realizing how much their work actually relied on theory. Famously he declared that "For the reader resolved to eschew theory and admit only definite observational facts, all astronomical books are banned. There are no purely observational facts about the heavenly bodies" (Eddington 1933, p. 17). Eddington did not want to imply that cosmological investigators were on shaky ground. Instead, he was making the case that theory was necessary for welding together the many different kinds of research that were necessary for studying the universe as a whole. Understanding the entire cosmos was a tricky business, and he wanted everyone to get used to using diverse sources of knowledge and embracing exploration instead of seeking certainty.

Eddington continued to highlight the disciplinary splits that were complicating the acceptance of an expanding universe. While he was fully persuaded by Lemaître, he understood that observers and classical astronomers were "not likely to be moved overmuch by ideas of bending of space or the gauge-invariance of the Riemann-Christoffel tensor" (Eddington 1933, p. 13). What he was referring to was the fact that the mathematical apparatus of general relativity was completely foreign, and quite intimidating, to classically trained astronomers. Even worse, categories such as "curved space-time" seemed downright metaphysical, and not something that serious scientists should be thinking about. But Eddington reminded astronomers that the redshifts of the spiral nebulae (which he was now happy to interpret as a genuine recession) was one of their

¹Lemaître, G. (1927)

greatest puzzles. An expanding universe, he suggested, should be of great interest to them if only because of its resolution of that mystery (Eddington 1930).

4. Beginnings

One of Lemaître's results that particularly fascinated Eddington was the demonstrated instability of a static Einstein universe. Once it was clear that an Einstein universe, if disturbed, would begin expanding in exactly the way that our universe seemed to be, Eddington began investigating this scenario closely (Eddington 1930). He put his research students to work investigating what could cause such disturbances, eventually concluding that the most likely source was a condensation of diffuse gas into stars and galaxies. This model, where an unstable Einstein universe sits for an indeterminate amount of time and then begins expanding, is sometimes called an Eddington universe. Besides its conceptual and mathematical elegance, it had a further appeal for him. It allowed astronomers and physicists to avoid a cosmological topic that he found quite problematic: the beginning of the universe. The widespread acceptance of an expanding universe led to speculation about what the universe was like deep in the past, when galaxies were packed tightly together. Lemaître proposed his "firework" model to describe this, in which a primeval atom exploded, hurling matter deep into space (Lemaître 1931a,b).

Eddington found this notion of a sudden start to the universe "repugnant" (Eddington 1931b, p. 450). He proposed that the advantage of his disturbed Einstein universe model was that the "initial small disturbance can happen without supernatural interference" (Eddington 1930, p. 670). He was a deeply religious man but refused to accept invocation of direct divine action in the physical world (Stanley 2007a). His model, he argued, provided the most consonant way of thinking about the beginning of the expansion:

There is at least a philosophical satisfaction in regarding the world as beginning to evolve infinitely slowly from a primitive uniform distribution in unstable equilibrium. Hence this case is the most attractive. (Eddington 1930, p. 672)

However, this argument was not quite sufficient for Eddington to escape having to discuss beginnings. Although his model lacked an initial explosion, there were other pressures for a distinct start to the universe. Even before the acceptance of Lemaître's theory, thermodynamic arguments for the need of a moment of creation had been widespread. The Victorian idea that there must have been a point of minimum entropy somewhere in the past, and a force to create that point, remained persuasive to many. Eddington was not convinced by this, but acknowledged that he could not disprove it either:

This should be regarded as the working-hypothesis of thermodynamics rather than its declaration of faith. It is one of those conclusions from which we can see no logical escape - only it suffers from the drawback that it is incredible. As a scientist I simply do not believe that the present order of things started off with a bang; unscientifically I feel equally unwilling to accept the implied discontinuity in the divine nature. But I can make no suggestion to evade the deadlock. (Eddington 1928, pp. 84-5)

He maintained that arguments about “the beginning of things lie almost beyond scientific argument” (Eddington 1933, p. 55). His use of the term “discontinuity” is key for understanding his position here. A discontinuity meant that an event was not part of the world of uniform natural laws that was the foundation of science. Thus, with no connection to natural laws, it could not be discussed in scientific terms. Instead, Eddington preferred to talk about beginnings as a matter of “aesthetic feeling.” He once described his own preference for a beginning that was “*not too unaesthetically abrupt*” (Eddington 1933, pp. 55-6).

Naturally, he argued that his static-to-expansion model best satisfied this criterion. He accepted that some would disagree, but in reply to those Eddington said “Have it your own way. And now let us get away from the Creation back to problems that we may possibly know something about” (Eddington 1933, p. 60). That is, the nature of the beginning of the universe was so far beyond the comprehension of both humans and science that it was pointless to discuss. For Eddington, a problem closely related to the creation of the universe was that of singularities. Both dealt with the problem of discontinuities. Eddington did not usually discuss the beginning of the universe in terms of singularities, but his general aversion to them can help explain why he was reluctant to allow a sudden beginning. The problem of singularities in general relativity appeared very early. Eddington first talked about them in his 1918 report with respect to de Sitter’s model. At the edge of the de Sitter universe, time stands still. Eddington thought of this singularity as being “merely the point of view” of the observer and having no true physical significance (Eddington 1918, p. 88). A few years later he explicitly suggested that this singularity at the edge of the universe was similar to the Schwarzschild singularity for matter. He concluded that since one could remove the de Sitter singularity through a coordinate transformation, one could probably remove all singularities this way (Eddington 1923, p. 165). Therefore, they were probably all illusory. By 1933, Eddington has decided that singularities were always artifacts of coordinate systems and had no physical meaning. A space cut off from interaction with the rest of the universe did not really make any sense to Eddington. His epistemology of science was profoundly dependent on the assumption that observation was literally necessary for the existence of the universe as we know it (Stanley 2007a). A place that could not be interacted with was inconceivable. This was probably also related to his thinking about collapsed stars in the 1930s (Stanley 2007b) The idea of matter creating a genuine singularity was simply bizarre to him. How could any scientific entity exist beyond even theoretical observation?

5. Conclusion

What Eddington would have considered his most important contribution to cosmology was actually widely rejected: his *Fundamental Theory* (Eddington 1948). He had been thinking about the big picture of cosmology in a highly idiosyncratic way. His idea was that there were fundamental connections between quantum physics and cosmology, particularly that the cosmological constant determined certain properties of subatomic particles. The calculus he used to develop this theory relied on several large number coincidences, such as the ratio of the electrical and gravitational forces being similar to the total number of the particles in the universe. Eddington saw the cosmological constant (or cosmical constant, as he called it) as the key to the unification of all physical forces. In particular, it set a universal radius of curvature that controlled

the size of electrons and protons, and indirectly the behavior of electromagnetic phenomena. The theory needed a closed universe with very particular properties, which he suspected could be derived a priori from considerations such as the degrees of freedom of the electron - claims for which he was vigorously criticized. The importance he placed on this unification was extreme; he even argued that the most important result of an expanding universe was that it had provided clues for these deeper issues of the unification of astronomy, relativity, and quantum mechanics. The cosmology itself he saw as secondary, saying it gave rise to no new philosophical issues (Eddington 1933, p. v).

In light of this, was Eddington significant for the story of the expanding universe? He certainly did not “discover” it in any sense. He did not perform the observations or develop the core theoretical models. But he was probably still critical to the story in several ways. He was a central clearinghouse for theories and data at a time when scientific communication was seriously compromised. Similarly, he was one of a handful of people who understood all the astronomical, physical, and mathematical aspects involved in early cosmology. From 1920 to 1930, that group had expanded from Eddington, de Sitter, and perhaps Silberstein and Einstein (though the founder of relativity’s knowledge of astronomy was rather thin) to include Friedmann, Lundmark, Lemaître, Jeans, Robertson, Tolman, etc. Key to this expansion were Eddington’s textbooks and pedagogy (Warwick 2003). He helped translate the astronomy for the physicists and vice versa, and helped create a core cluster of methods, expectations, and goals for what it meant to do cosmology. Even the physical meaning of general relativity required years of effort to bring into consensus. Eddington was also critical to making the case for the importance of theory in studying the universe: he made cosmology something you could do at a desk. Finally, he reminds us that many of the basic categories of an expanding universe (e.g. that redshifted spirals indicated an expansion) were not at all obvious to the investigators at the time. Scientific developments whose significance seems clear in retrospect actually required a great deal of effort, thought, and persuasion to establish. The “discovery” of the expanding universe was more complicated than we might think.

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